

Fuzzy Image Segmentation Technique Applied in Digital Watermarking

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Abstract- In this work, we present a novel fuzzy picture segmentation-based watermarking strategy for image copyright protection in the geographical domain. In order to find the best places to hide a watermark, the fuzzy image method uses a features map (edges and regions) that are less perceptible to the human eye. Our approach maximises both imperceptibility and robustness, which are known to be inversely correlated. The PSNR, SSIM, and two similarity metrics based on the fuzzy logic S1, S2' were used to assess the transparency performance of the suggested strategy. The evaluation's findings show how resilient the suggested approach is against popular image processing operators. Because our approach merely makes use of basic processes like fuzzy picture segmentation and image fuzziness, it is also efficient.

Keywords- Digital watermarking, Fuzzy logic, Fuzzy image processing.

I.INTRODUCTION

As Internet usage increased, information concealment emerged as a significant field. The topic of information hiding is relatively new and is expanding at an exponential rate [1, 2]. Digital watermarking and steganography comprise the two categories of information-hiding applications used in digital photographs. Digital watermarking, a subset of information hiding, offers a reliable method for digital media data integrity, security, authentication, and copyright protection.

Digital image watermarking works by embedding some hidden information into the image data while maintaining the quality of the watermarked data and allowing the watermark to be detected under various intentional and unintentional attacks. In other words, watermarking should be robust, but there are conflicting methods for achieving imperceptibility and robustness. Striking a proper balance between robustness and imperceptibility is a crucial challenge. Robustness is the capacity to withstand certain harmful attacks, such those that target common image processing processes (such as clipping, filtering, enhancing, compression, etc.), which is a crucial concern in digital watermarking. The original image's imperceptibility shouldn't be noticeably affected by the watermark. Put otherwise, we need to make sure that an unauthorised user is unaware that the watermark is present. The exceptional perceptual quality of the protected image is guaranteed by imperceptibility [3].

There are many different methods to classify watermarking processes. There are three main techniques for adding and removing a watermark from still digital photos. These three types of approaches include colour space, transform domain, and spatial domain. The watermark embedding in the spatial domain technique [4] is accomplished by directly altering the host image's pixel values. The least significant bit (LSB) approach is the one that is most frequently utilised in the spatial domain strategy. The discrete cosine transform (DCT), discrete Fourier transform (DFT), discrete wavelet transform (DWT), etc. are some examples of transformation methods that are used in the transform domain methodology [5] to first transform the host image into the frequency domain. then, the watermark modifies the transform domain coefficients. Usually, the inverse transform is used to produce the watermarked image. The image is changed from RGB colour space to another colour space, such as YUV colour space, in the colour space watermarking technique [6].

Many adaptive watermarking techniques for digital images have been put out in recent years. One particularly good option is to use the adaptive watermarking technique, which incorporates the elements of the human visual system (HVS) model [7, 8]. Intelligent algorithms, like neural networks and fuzzy methods, have been incorporated into digital watermarking techniques recently. These algorithms can enhance the robustness and visual quality of the watermarked image at the same time. A fuzzy logic-based adaptive watermarking methodology was proposed by Lou et al. in [9]. A digital watermarking approach based on fuzzy clustering was proposed by Wu et al. [10] in the DCT domain. It can manage the embedding strength of different blocks in an adaptive manner. A dynamic fuzzy inference system-based adaptive picture watermarking approach was presented by Sakr et al. [11]. A Fuzzy-ART based adaptive digital watermarking system in the DCT domain was proposed by Chang et al. in [12]. Novel hardware for an adaptive encrypted watermarking technique based on fuzzy logic was proposed by Lunde et al. [13]. Oueslati et al. introduced an adaptive watermarking system in [14] that operates in the wavelet domain and takes advantage of a human visual system (HVS) and a Fuzzy Inference System (FIS).

In this research, we offer a novel fuzzy logic-based watermarking algorithm for copyright protection. To find the best places to hide a watermark, the fuzzy image segmentation technique is used. Due to the human eye's reduced sensitivity to changes in textured areas compared to smooth parts. The watermark is embedded in the cover image's feature pixels, or edges components, by means of this technique. As a result, fewer computations are needed.

The structure of this document is as follows. In Section 2, the idea of fuzzy image processing is explained. In Section 3, a method for introducing and detecting watermarks is proposed. Section 4 displays the outcomes of the experiment. This paper is concluded in Section 5.

II. FUZZY IMAGE PROCESSING

It is not exclusive to fuzzy image processing theory. It is an assortment of many fuzzy image processing techniques. However, the definition that follows can be considered an attempt to draw those lines: The umbrella term for all methods that comprehend, represent, and handle images, their constituent parts, and their features as fuzzy sets is fuzzy image processing. The problem to be solved and the fuzzy technique used will determine the representation and processing [15].

The following are the requirements for fuzzy image processing that are most crucial:

1. When it comes to processing and representing knowledge, fuzzy approaches are effective tools.
2. Ambiguity and vagueness can be effectively managed using fuzzy approaches.
3. Expert knowledge is required in many image-processing applications (such as object recognition and scene analysis) in order to get past the challenges.

The three primary steps of fuzzy image processing are image fuzzification, membership value modification, and, if required, image defuzzification. Fig. 1 depicts the general fuzzy image processing method.

Fig. 1. The general structure of fuzzy image processing.

The reason for the fuzzification and defuzzification processes is that we don't have fuzzy hardware. Fuzzy approaches can therefore be used to process images through the processes of coding the image data (fuzzification) and decoding the results (defuzzification). As can be seen in Fig. 2, the adjustment of membership values in the middle phase is where fuzzy image processing really shines. The membership values are altered by suitable fuzzy techniques once the picture data have been fuzzy-analyzed (converted from the gray-level plane to the membership plane). This can take the form of fuzzy integration, fuzzy rule-based method, fuzzy clustering, and so forth [16].

Fig. 2. Steps of fuzzy image processing.

III. PROPOSED WATERMARKING ALGORITHM

The method we provide here is predicated on using fuzzy image segmentation on the digital image that will have a watermark added to it. The key steps of the suggested watermark extraction and embedding techniques are covered in this section. Fig. 3 shows the flowchart for the suggested watermarking algorithm.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of proposed watermarking method.

A. Image fuzzification

First, a fuzzy image (fuzzy data set) is created from an original image (crisp data set) using fuzzification. We employ a fuzzy gaussian function for the purpose of fuzzifying. According to fuzzy set theory, an image X with dimensions of $M \times N$ and L grey levels of pixels can be interpreted as a collection of fuzzy singletons, each with a membership value [17]. A fuzzy image can therefore be represented as:

$$X = \bigcup_i \bigcup_j x_{ij} \mid \mu(x_{ij}). \quad (1)$$

In essence, the grey value's membership function indicates whether a pixel belongs to a particular class. The fuzzy Gaussian function has the following equation:

$$\mu(x) = e^{-f_1 \times (x - f_2)^2}. \quad (2)$$

The spread (f_1) and the midpoint (f_2) are the equation's inputs. Typically, the spread falls between 0.01 and 1, where a higher value corresponds to a steeper distribution around the midpoint. (The value by default is 0.1). The mean of the input data is used to determine the default value for midway.

B. Noise removal

Removing noise from an image successfully without compromising its basic structure of edges and corners is a fundamental problem in image analysis. This phase involves removing noise from the image using a fuzzy filter.

Let X_{mn} represent the grey level of the pixel at position (m, n) . The membership value $m(u) \times$ of any pixel in X_c 's neighbourhood is provided by [17] if X_c is the central pixel grey level.

$$\mu(x_{ij}) = \exp\left[\frac{-(x_c - x_{ij})^2}{\alpha}\right] \exp\left[\frac{-d^2}{\beta}\right]. \quad (3)$$

where f_3 and α are two scaling factors that control how flat the membership function is, and d is the distance between the central pixel X and the nearby pixel ij 's.

The weights used to average the pixels in the neighbourhood W are the membership values. The fuzzy filter algorithm can be used in the following ways: First, identify a neighbourhood W of a reasonable size for a central pixel, X_c .

Finding the membership value $I_i(u)$ for each pixel ij x in the neighbourhood is the second step. x Third, this means that the adjusted grey value of the central pixel can be found using:

$$x'_c = \frac{\lfloor \sum \sum \mu_{ij} x_{ij} \rfloor}{\lfloor \sum \sum \mu_{ij} \rfloor}, \forall (i, j) \in W, x_{ij} \neq x_c. \quad (4)$$

C. Fuzzy image segmentation

To identify the best areas to include a watermark, we create a features map in this stage. To compute the values of the features map, we employ a thresholding approach based on fuzzy edge detection for picture segmentation. Using a features map, the image is divided into two regions: edges and non-edges.

The method of segmenting a picture is used to divide it into various sections or pixel groupings. Partitions are actually distinct elements in an image with the same colour or texture. A collection of regions that together include the full image or a collection of contours that are retrieved from the image are the outcomes of image segmentation. Pixels are divided into fuzzy sets by fuzzy segmentation, meaning that each pixel may partially belong to several sets and areas of the image [15, 17]. Finding the ideal threshold T and dividing the scene into two significant regions—objects (O) and backdrop (B)—are the two steps in the thresholding problem. Examples of these segments include:

$$\begin{aligned} O &= \{(m, n) \mid I_{mn} \geq T\} \\ B &= \{(m, n) \mid I_{mn} < T\} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Using fuzzy thresholding, the image is divided into two fuzzy sets, O and B , which represent the background and the object, respectively, by determining the membership distributions μ_O and μ_B that correspond to these areas. Here, we employ the fuzzy thresholding approach, which accounts for fluctuations in each region's gray-values while simultaneously minimising fuzziness in the thresholded description. The membership function is defined as follows and is used to show each neighborhood's level of edginess:

$$\mu_{\tilde{O}}(I_{mn}) = \begin{cases} [1 + \frac{v - I_{mn}}{k}]^{-1} & \text{if } I_{mn} \geq T \\ 0 & \text{if } I_{mn} < T \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where the parameter k determines how fuzzy the segmented description is, and v is the mean gray-value of O . For B as well, a comparable membership assignment was used. They used the hard threshold T to clearly classify the pixels into object or background regions.

D. Watermark embedding

Given that the HVS is unable to discern variations in edge regions, edges are crucial to how pictures are perceived. As a result, we place watermarks in areas that the features map designates as "Edges."

Following the calculation of the membership values derived from the fuzzy segmentation process, as indicated by equation (6). The map of fuzzy features (edges) is extractable. The locations in the original image where the watermark bits will be recorded will be determined by the feature values in the interval $[0-1]$. This is accomplished by comparing the membership value of the fuzzy segmentation operation to the mean value of the membership values. If the membership value is higher, the watermark bit is stored in the same location in the original image. This process keeps going till the watermark bits run out. By altering a particular bit of the pixels, the watermark is inserted into the chosen pixels. The original image's pixels in which the watermark bits are placed must meet the following requirements:

$$\mu_{\tilde{O}}(f_{mn}) > M_m, \quad (7)$$

where M_m represents mean value for membership values of the fuzzy segmentation operation.

E. Watermark extraction

The opposite of watermark embedding is watermark extraction. All that is required of us is the secret key and the threshold value. We employ the membership value file under the same suppositions as stated in formula (6). Image segmentation, noise reduction, and image fuzzifying are the processes. The watermark portions are extracted from the watermarked image's pixels, which must meet the subsequent requirements:

$$\mu_{\tilde{O}}(f_{mn}) < M_m. \quad (8)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The suggested watermarking approach is evaluated using a number of photographs taken from the IVE 2009 image database [18]. Figures 4.a2 and 4.a1 show the original pictures.

The original photos with watermarks are shown in Figs. 4.b 1 and 4.b 2.

Fig. 4. (a1&a2) Original images, (b1&b2) Watermarked image

We assess the robustness and imperceptibility of the suggested approach. Two similarity measures that are based on fuzzy logic are used to evaluate transparency [19].

$$S_1(A,B)=1-\left(\frac{1}{MN} \sum_{x=1}^M \sum_{y=1}^N |\mu_A(x,y) - \mu_B(x,y)|^r\right)^{\frac{1}{r}} \quad (9)$$

where $r>0$. The similarity measure S_2 is based on the fuzzy minkowski distance, and the observation that the smaller the distance between original image A and watermarked image B.

$$S_2(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = \frac{\sum_{x,y}^{MN} \min(\mu_A(x,y), \mu_B(x,y))}{\sum_{x,y}^{MN} \max(\mu_A(x,y), \mu_B(x,y))} \quad (10)$$

where $\mu_A(x,y)$ and $\mu_B(x,y)$ are fuzzy membership values of the pixel of the two images A and B respectively. The quality evaluation results of proposed watermarking algorithm by using S_j , S_j , PSNR and SSIM [14] measures are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Quality evaluation for proposed algorithm.

Quality measures	Image 1	Image 2
S_1	0.931	0.905
S_2	0.921	0.881
PSNR (dB)	43.991	42.94
SSIM	0.922	0.832

The suggested algorithm's resilience is assessed using a few assaults from the Stirmark and Checkmark benchmarks. In order to extract the watermarking information, we attempt to apply several types of operations to the watermarked data. Following the watermark extraction process, we employ comparable measurements of the extracted and referenced watermarks for validation; this is characterised by the Normalised Correlation (NC). This is the definition of the formula used to determine similarity:

$$NC = \frac{\sum_k (W_k \cdot W_k^*)}{\sum_k (W_k^*)^2}, \quad k=1, \dots, L, \quad (11)$$

where W_k and W_k are referenced and extracted watermarks and L is length of watermark bits. Here, the size of watermark is (200 bits) and the watermark repeatedly inserted into the original image. The robustness evaluation is reported in Table 2.

V.CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a fuzzy logic-based watermarking system in this research that can be applied to image copyright.

Table 2. Robustness evaluation by NC values.

Attack Types	Image 1	Image 2
Jpeg compression 3%	0.918	0.923
Jpeg compression 15%	0.875	0.889
Jpeg compression2000 3%	0.865	0.876
Jpeg compression2000 15%	0.811	0.824
Gaussian noise $\sigma =50\%$	0.915	0.93
Blurring	0.882	0.895
Winner filtering	0.916	0.931
Median filtering	0.972	0.981
Sharping	0.964	0.978

The findings of the experiment indicate that the degradation caused by the watermark's embedding is too little to be seen. Therefore, a better trade-off between robustness and transparency can be achieved by the suggested watermarking approach. Furthermore, this algorithm's robustness is sufficient to withstand attacks like as blurring, compression, and gaussian noise. Future research will concentrate on strengthening the watermarks' resistance to additional threats and improving the algorithms' robustness and capacity.

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